

The Digital Critical Edition of the *Capitula* to the Octateuch in the Tours Bibles

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1. Introduction

This document outlines the editorial choices made for the digital edition of the *capitula* to the Octateuch as transmitted in the Tours Bibles, with the aim of sharing the underlying technical and scholarly considerations and facilitating the reuse of both the edition and the associated data in other research contexts or through other tools.

The digital edition of the *capitula* to the Octateuch are part of the PRIN 2022 PNRR project *DoBiPS – Data Oriented Biblical Paratext Studies*, awarded for the 2023-2025 biennium to the research units at the Universities of Udine (P.I. E. Colombi) and Cassino (P.I. R. Casavecchia) under the competitive PRIN PNRR call – National Recovery and Resilience Plan, Mission 4 "Education and Research", funded by the European Union's NextGenerationEU programme (protocol no. P2022ZW4AW).

The overarching goal of these editions is to investigate the transmission dynamics of these often-neglected paratexts by focusing on three relatively homogeneous contexts of manuscript production – namely, the Tours Bibles, the so-called Atlantic Bibles, and the Bibles in Beneventan script. For each of these three groups, the aim is to reconstruct the form assumed by the *capitula*, assess their possible dependence on a shared archetype, and analyse the relationships among the witnesses within each group.

The editions of the *capitula* prefixed to the Octateuch in the Tours Bibles have been encoded in XML/TEI and rendered for publication and visualisation using the software EVT ([Edition Visualization Technology](#)).

Although the TEI standard might appear somewhat oversized for the relative simplicity of the material, it was chosen for its status as a broadly recognised and widely adopted standard that ensures long-term interoperability – both within and beyond the scope of the project – as well as compatibility with a wide range of visualisation and data processing tools. Its extensibility and increasing ecosystem of related tools also offer significant potential for future development.

The choice to visualise the edition using EVT reflects current scholarly concerns with ecological sustainability and *minimal computing*. EVT is a robust and flexible tool that supports the independent configuration of visualisations with a manageable learning curve, thereby avoiding the need for external technical intervention or custom-built solutions that often require dedicated hosting and risk obsolescence at the end of the projects that created them. These considerations led us to favour what [Elena Pierazzo](#) has termed a *prêt-à-porter* approach to

digital editions, whose serial nature we regard as an additional advantage – almost as if contributing to the creation of a series of editions published through the same platform, with similar visual features that facilitate access and navigation by the user, who is not forced to relearn from scratch the functioning of each individual *haute couture* edition in order to benefit from its textual and methodological innovations.

The adoption of EVT also enables the publication not only of the data but of the visualised edition itself via the GitHub platform. This solution ensures long-term sustainability, while also making the research outputs FAIR and openly accessible.

The digital editions are available –progressively expanded and updated – through a dedicate [GitHub Pages site](#), while the XML-TEI source files are accessible in the corresponding [GitHub repository](#).

The choice of a *prêt-à-porter* solution is not without its cost, as it entails a constant negotiation between specific scholarly requirements and the general functionalities provided by the software. In more than a few cases—discussed below—this has required substantial compromises between the desired granularity of the encoding, the methodological soundness of the markup (which we were keen not to 'force' merely to obtain a desired visual outcome), and the constraints of actual visualisation. Nevertheless, this seemed to us a reasonable trade-off in light of the advantages outlined above, and in some respects even a form of containment with respect to the many options offered by the TEI Guidelines for encoding the same phenomenon – options that are often inversely proportional to the degree of interoperability across different projects.

2. Manuscripts and their Description

The witnesses considered for this edition represent nearly the entire corpus of surviving pandects produced in the scriptorium of Tours from the abbacy of Alcuin onwards.¹ In order to contextualise the version of the *capitula* circulating in Tours, two of the earliest known witnesses of these *capitula* have also been collated for comparison: the Maurdrampus Bible – represented for the Octateuch by the manuscript Amiens, *Bibliothèques d'Amiens Métropole* (formerly *Bibliothèque municipale*), Ms. 6, produced at Corbie under Abbot Maurdrampus – and the so-called 'Tours Octateuch' (Tours, *Bibliothèque municipale*, 10), whose dating and provenance remain debated, though it was most likely produced at Tours between 790 and 800.

The manuscript descriptions, accessible via the icon in the top left corner of the edition interface, are limited to a set of essential data, in order to ensure consistency even for witnesses that have not yet received extensive scholarly attention and for which only brief descriptions are available and no autoptic examination has been conducted for these. Each entry includes:

¹ The only manuscripts not yet consulted are Monza, *Biblioteca Capitolare*, G. 1 and Basel, *Universitätsbibliothek*, A. N. I. 3.

the full shelfmark; place and date of production;² physical composition, layout, and page dimensions; and the folios containing the capitula for the biblical book concerned.

Fig. 1: manuscript description

As illustrated by the template in Fig. 1, particular care has been taken to ensure the hypertextual and interoperable structure of the edition: wherever available, the template includes a link to the persistent identifier assigned by [Biblissima+](#), the French research infrastructure dedicated to the study of written and graphic cultural heritage from Antiquity to the Renaissance, which aggregates metadata and digitised sources from a wide range of catalogues and collections.

Each manuscript is also associated, where possible, with its identifier in [Trismegistos](#), the interdisciplinary portal focused on texts and documents from the ancient world, designed to link together metadata from different corpora and projects.

If a [Biblissima+](#) ID is not yet available, a link is provided to [ARCA](#), the manuscript database developed by the Institut de Recherche et d'Histoire des Textes (IRHT-CNRS), which provides structured descriptions and identifiers for medieval manuscripts in the Latin West.

As an additional reference, the catalogue number assigned to each manuscript by Bernhard Bischoff in his *Katalog der festländischen Handschriften des neunten Jahrhunderts* (Wiesbaden 1998-2014) is also included.

Within the <surrogates> element – which, according to the TEI Guidelines, «contains information about any representations of the manuscript or other object being described which may exist in the holding institution or elsewhere» – hyperlinks have been provided to: the digitised reproduction; one or more online descriptions of the manuscript; the IIF manifest; and, for manuscripts listed in the *Codices Latini Antiquiores* (CLA), the corresponding entry in the [Earlier Latin Manuscripts database](#).

The edition of the *capitula* prepared by Donatien de Bruyne (*Sommaires, divisions et rubriques de la Bible latine*, Paris 1914) has been encoded not only as a bibliographical reference but also as a witness, in order to make immediately visible any deviations from the reconstructed text considered representative of the Tours tradition.

² For the Tours Bibles, the periodisation established by Bonifatius Fischer in *Lateinische Bibelhandschriften im frühen Mittelalter* (Freiburg, 1985, pp. 256–269) has been followed.

At present, EVT's critical edition mode does not support direct linking between specific textual passages and corresponding regions of manuscript images. However, digital reproductions of the folios containing the *capitula* for each edition can still be accessed by enabling the text-image view mode via the icon in the top-right corner of the interface (Fig. 2); the images will appear sequentially in the left-hand pane. Users may navigate through the sequence of images either by scrolling directly within the image pane or via the horizontal slider located below it.

To facilitate alignment between text and image, reference points have been encoded in the XML to mark the beginning of each folio (recto and verso) for all witnesses.

Fig. 2: Text-image visualisation

2. The Critical Text: Philological, Technical, and Editorial Criteria

The editions adopt a relatively conservative editorial stance, partly also because users can access the text of each individual witness by clicking on its siglum; accordingly, we tried to render the transcription as close as possible to that of the manuscript source. Although the full potential of a diplomatic-interpretative transcription was not exploited – since this would have caused irreconcilable conflicts with the critical edition view in EVT (the two modes are currently mutually incompatible) – we opted for a minimalist approach. Capitalisation is limited to the initial letter of each *capitulum*, reflecting the manuscript evidence, and punctuation has been kept to a bare minimum.

Characters such as *e* with cedilla and the ligatures *ae* and *oe* have been encoded using Unicode and recorded as graphical variants, given their potential to generate grammatical

and/or semantic variation (e.g. a feminine genitive singular misread as an adverb due to loss of the diphthong). Abbreviations have generally been silently expanded, except in rare ambiguous cases, since their markup with `<choice> <orig> <reg>` and `<choice> <abbr> <expan>` would not be properly rendered in EVT's critical edition view, and would have unnecessarily burdened the apparatus.

An exception regarding the expansion of abbreviations was made for the opening and closing headings of the capitula. When these appear in full form in the manuscripts, one can observe a number of errors and *ad sensum* concordances (e.g. the frequent *incipit capitula*) that make the expansion of abbreviations uncertain. Since, in EVT's critical edition mode, the use of `<choice>`, `<abbr>`, and `<expan>` results in the abbreviated and expanded forms being displayed consecutively – thus simulating a variant reading – this approach was avoided. For the sake of internal consistency, we adopted the same convention as in the transcription of headings in [the biblical manuscripts database developed by the DoBiPS project](#): letters actually present in the manuscript heading are rendered in uppercase (without reproducing the abbreviation marks), while the presumed expansion appears in lowercase.

The drawback of this strategy is that variations in the abbreviated form are treated as distinct readings and displayed as such. To mitigate this effect, witnesses are grouped according to similarity in heading structure (e.g. whether or not they explicitly mention the biblical book to which the capitula refer), whereas elsewhere in the critical apparatus witnesses are listed in chronological order.

One methodological priority from the outset was the opportunity to exploit the spatial flexibility of the digital edition in order to implement a fine-grained encoding strategy that would systematically record the genetic dimension of the text—even for minor details or corrections made at different stages (and possibly by the original scribe during transcription). These elements are typically excluded from traditional critical apparatuses for reasons of space and readability, yet they can prove crucial in reconstructing the genesis of variants and the relationships among witnesses.

The adopted solution was to encode textual layers using the `@varSeq` attribute, followed by the progressive number of the layer. In EVT, this encoding results in the juxtaposition of both readings within the apparatus, but it has no effect on the main critical text or on the display of individual witnesses, where only the first encoded layer (`@varSeq="1"`) is shown.

To alert the reader to the presence of subsequent corrective layers, a visual strategy was employed in the configuration file: only the `@varSeq` attribute is made selectable as a filter for variants and is highlighted in red. This allows users, when viewing an individual witness (Fig. 3, right panel), to easily identify those readings which, when clicked, reveal further textual layers. Other types of witness-specific variation, by contrast, are rendered in the critical text displayed in the left panel.

In addition to enhancing transparency for human users, this multi-layered annotation also provides a structured foundation for future computational analyses, particularly in tracing the diachronic evolution of a text across copying stages or identifying contamination patterns between witnesses. The explicit separation of successive textual states can facilitate more refined phylogenetic modelling and support the training of machine-learning models on editorially curated data with internal stratification.

Fig. 3: Highlighting of corrective layers in individual witnesses (right-hand panel)

By consulting the XML encoding – accessible via the apparatus panel – it is also possible to retrieve systematically recorded details about the manner in which one textual layer transitions into the next. For instance, the first stratum (varSeq="1") may be marked by "subpunctuation", "erasure", or "strikethrough", while the second (varSeq="2") may involve "overstrike" or "transposition marks" (transpMarks). The encoding also specifies the physical location of the correction (e.g. "above", "marginal", "intercolumnar") and the hand responsible for it. Given that a more granular distinction is often unfeasible – especially for minimal interventions – a simplified tripartite classification has been adopted: the main scribe (xml:id="#m"), a generally later hand (xml:id="#l"), and unknown hand (xml:id="#u") when the chronology of the intervention cannot be established.

A second aspect—entirely experimental and certainly open to future revision—emerged from a deliberate methodological reflection and concerns the classification of textual variants. The longstanding debate over the editor's subjectivity and the interpretative constraints imposed on readers by editorial choices has, predictably, intensified in the context of digital editions. Here, the possibility of presenting the textual witness in a diplomatic – or at least editorially unaltered – form has brought renewed attention to the delicate question of the editor's responsibility and the boundaries of their interpretative agency. This agency is exercised not only in the constitution of the critical text itself but, more fundamentally, in the evaluation of variants, which in turn determines the relational architecture among the witnesses.

In a digital critical edition, this process can – and indeed should – be made transparent through appropriate encoding, by systematically classifying each instance of variation. Yet this very transparency also systematises the inherent subjectivity of the classification process, rendering it more explicit and, consequently, more open to critique.

In an effort to engage constructively with this debate, we have organised the main attributes responsible for capturing textual variation according to two parallel criteria:

– The **@type** attribute is used to encode two distinct but complementary aspects of textual variation: the structural nature of the phenomenon and, where applicable, the degree of divergence from the accepted lemma. The values "omission", "addition", and "transposition" indicate the formal type of intervention observed – whether content is lacking, added, or rearranged. Although "transposition" does not affect character count and is not easily identifiable by automatic means, it has been retained in this classification because it constitutes an objectively recognisable structural phenomenon once annotated by the editor. These structural labels are independent of the amount of text involved and serve to categorise the variation on a formal level.

In contrast, the values "minor", "maior", and "substantive" apply to cases in which an alternative reading replaces the lemma and express the degree of divergence in strictly quantitative terms, measured by character count: "minor" denotes a variation of up to two characters, "maior" up to 50% of the lemma, and "substantive" more than 50%. These thresholds were defined heuristically in order to balance granularity and robustness in automatic processing across lemmata of different lengths.

Two additional values are included to support scenarios relevant to digital philology and computational workflows: "lem" is used when a variant reading coincides with the accepted lemma – typically when a correction restores the original reading – while the label "unclear" is used both when the variant cannot be assessed due to illegibility in the digital reproduction – in which case the cause is explicitly indicated as "digitisation" via a separate attribute – and when the text is compromised by material damage, with the cause noted as "damage".

This non-semantic evaluation of textual variance is intended as a preliminary conceptual exercise aimed at assessing the potential compatibility with downstream processing workflows – both in the modelling of data and in the design of analytical pipelines beginning with handwritten text recognition (HTR). By relying on formal, character-level criteria rather than semantic interpretation, this kind of encoding strategy could enable the application of algorithmic methods for the classification, clustering, and comparison of textual variants across witnesses. It could also promote consistency and reproducibility in contexts where human interpretation introduces levels of variability that current automated systems cannot reliably accommodate. This attempt is deliberately reductive and exploratory, but future developments may refine the assessment further, for instance by incorporating edit-distance metrics (e.g. Levenshtein) to support finer-grained distinctions where needed.

In the case of "substantive" variants, an additional qualitative classification is provided through the **@subtype** attribute, which specifies whether the variant is considered "error" or "adiaphoric". This distinction reflects the editor's philological assessment of the impact of the variant on meaning or textual coherence, and aims to complement the purely quantitative measure with a minimal yet meaningful semantic evaluation. While not machine-detectable at this stage, this annotation can support downstream filtering and analysis—especially in hybrid workflows that combine algorithmic processing with expert validation.

– The **@cause** attribute is used instead to provide the qualitative assessment of the likely origin of a textual variant. The possible values reflect a typology grounded in traditional textual criticism, codicology, and paleography:

- "slip" is used for minor, often momentary lapses (e.g. eye skips or brief inattentiveness), typically resulting in small omissions or alterations at the level of individual letters;
- "misspelling" applies when a word or a substantial part of it is incorrectly written, often due to auditory confusion or misunderstanding, leading to the replacement of one meaningful word with another;
- "orthographic" designates graphical variation not considered erroneous (e.g. variation in the rendering of a cedilla or Latin transliteration of Hebrew names); when relevant, @ana="hebrew" is used to specify that the variation involves a proper name of Semitic origin;
- "correction" is assigned when the variant represents a scribe's attempt to restore the lemma and is functionally equivalent to it (often encoded via a secondary <varSeq>); in contrast, "falseEmendation" is used when the intervention fails to restore the correct reading;
- "grammatical" captures deviations involving inflectional morphology – such as conjugation or declension changes;
- "space" indicates that an omission or abbreviation may have been motivated by lack of space in the writing area (e.g. end of line or column);
- "numbering" refers to misnumbering or other issues related to numeric sequences, especially common in structured paratexts like chapter headings;
- "paleographicConfusion" is used for cases where the scribe appears to have misread or miswritten characters due to visual similarity in the script;
- Classical categories of mechanical error are also represented: "diplography", "haplography", "homeoteleuton", and "homeoarchy" each denote specific types of visual interference arising from repetition or similarity at the beginning or end of lines or phrases;
- "rubrication" is applied when the variant arises from the erroneous omission or faulty intervention of the rubricator;
- "VetusLatina" and "Vulgate" are used when the variant can be ascribed to the influence of the Old Latin or the Vulgate version of the biblical text, respectively;
- Finally, "unknown" is reserved for instances where the cause of the variant cannot be properly evaluated.

An additional technical complication emerged from the way EVT handles the automatic generation of positive apparatus entries in critical editions, particularly in the presence of lacunae and nested variants. When a witness lacks an entire segment due to a lacuna—either material or due to digitisation issues—EVT signals the beginning and end of the lacuna in the text panel. However, in the automatically generated apparatus, the same witness is still included by default in nested variant groups, even though it should be excluded from those readings. A similar issue arises with additions or partial headings: if a variant affects only one word of a longer segment that is itself missing from a given witness, EVT will still include that lacunose witness in the nested variant unless the variant is explicitly split and manually annotated. This limitation can also cause erroneous inclusion of witnesses that do not contain the added passage at all, simply because some variation exists within it.

Although EVT2 nominally supports lacunae in critical editions—by allowing the tagging of <lacuna> elements—this support does not extend to automatic exclusion of lacunose witnesses from nested variants unless additional manual intervention is applied.

While it is technically possible to correct this by forcing the apparatus to list only the witnesses that truly transmit the lemma, through explicit use of @wit attributes inside <lem> elements, this approach is cumbersome and error-prone when working with a large number of witnesses. In our encoding, this strategy was considered but only rarely employed; instead, we adopted a systematic policy of fragmenting variants into the smallest possible <app> units whenever the visualisation proved ambiguous or misleading. This approach resolved most of the display issues, and aligned well with our character-count-based classification of variants (as outlined above), which benefits from shorter, well-defined variant spans.

Nonetheless, it should be noted that this segmentation strategy, while effective for visualisation purposes, introduces challenges when analysing variants that span longer textual units—such as entire clauses or syntactically meaningful sequences—potentially limiting broader philological reasoning. This issue becomes particularly relevant when dealing with textual typologies that exhibit more complex syntactic structures than those typically found in capitula, and will require further theoretical reflection in future work.